

USE OF THE INTERNET AS A DIDACTIC TOOL IN DISTANCE LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the problem of creating an Internet platform for English language teachers. Such an Internet platform is considered as an innovative didactic tool that performs all the functions of didactic tools and can be used for distance learning in English.

Keywords: *Internet platform, e-learning, didactic tool, distance learning of a foreign language*

Аннотация: Статья посвящена проблеме создания интернет-платформы для преподавателей английского языка. Такая интернет-платформа рассматривается как инновационное дидактическое средство, которое выполняет все функции дидактических средств и может быть использовано для дистанционного обучения английскому языку.

Ключевые слова: *интернет-платформа, электронное обучение, дидактическое средство, дистанционное обучение иностранному языку*

Annotatsiya: Maqola ingliz tili o'qituvchilari uchun Internet platformasini yaratish muammosiga bag'ishlangan. Bunday Internet-platforma didaktik vositalarning barcha funktsiyalarini bajaradigan innovatsion didaktik vosita sifatida qaraladi va ingliz tilida masofaviy ta'lim uchun foydalanish mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: *Internet platformasi, elektron ta'lim, didaktik vosita, chet tilini masofaviy o'qitish*

In the modern world, there is an urgent need to use information technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language, since they not only facilitate the process itself, but

also expand the audience of students. The ability to use an Internet platform for classes allows the teacher to conduct a full lesson in real time using the resources of the Internet platform. However, most teachers are wary of this type of teaching, preferring a traditional lesson to the latest technologies.

This article will focus on the Internet platform as a didactic tool for teaching a foreign language in the context of additional education. Our task is to compare traditional didactic tools and their functions and the Internet platform as an innovative tool, to identify their role in the modern process of teaching foreign languages.

The concept of a didactic tool is considered both in a narrow and in a broad sense. According to the opinion of V.A. Slastina didactic means are objects that are sensorimotor stimuli that affect the senses of students and facilitate their direct and indirect knowledge of the world [3, p. 276]. According to the author, didactic tools include all objects used in the educational process and facilitating the process itself, such as textbooks, school supplies, computers, etc. We are interested in a broader understanding of the very concept of a didactic tool. Based on the dictionary of S.M. Vishnyakova, we adhere to the following definition. “Didactic means are the means by which learning goals are realized. They are divided into material (didactic material) and non-material means (methods and techniques of teaching, forms of organizing educational and cognitive activities)” [1, p. 113]. That is, a didactic tool is not only what a teacher uses in the process of pedagogical activity, but also a way of organizing this activity.

Traditional material didactic means are usually classified according to sensory modality [2]. That is, based on which sense organs are involved in the process of perceiving information by students. Guided by this feature, we can divide didactic means into visual, auditory, audiovisual, simulators and universal. We can classify the Internet platform as a universal didactic tool, since in the process of perceiving information when learning using the Internet platform, hearing and vision are involved, and certain skills are also being developed using modern simulators (for example, electronic cards with new words).

When understanding a didactic tool as a means of an intangible nature, we are dealing with didactic forms of organizing training, among which traditionally general class forms of organizing classes (lesson, conference, seminar, etc.), group forms of teaching (group work in the lesson, creative assignments), individual forms of work in class and at home (written exercises, work with literature, etc.) [3]. The capabilities of the Internet platform make it possible to conduct class-wide forms of organizing classes without affecting the quality of training. This is evidenced by the use of webinar platforms for training employees of world-famous companies. For example, the webinar platform myown-conference.ru has the ability to conduct a webinar with one or more presenters and participants in real time, which corresponds to the traditional form of training - a lecture. Group forms of work are usually implemented by creating specific chats between webinar members. Individual works are sent to the group chat or to the e-mail of the seminar leader.

Thus, we can conclude that the Internet platform as a didactic tool is in no way inferior to traditional material didactic tools. Organization of training is also possible using the Internet platform without loss of quality of training.

The term “e-learning” is understood as the organization of educational activities with the use of information contained in databases and used in the implementation of educational programs and information technologies, technical means that ensure its processing, as well as information and telecommunication networks that ensure the transmission of this information via communication lines, interaction between students and teaching staff [3]. That is, we can include not only distance learning as e-learning, but also independent learning using information technology.

Distance learning undoubtedly has a number of advantages over traditional learning. The first and main advantage, of course, is freedom of access. That is, students can study almost anywhere, receiving the quality of education that is only available in big cities. That is, students have equal opportunities regardless of their place of residence. Another very important criterion in favor of choosing distance learning is the opportunity to study with teachers abroad, gain advanced knowledge in scientific fields, attend lectures from the best universities in the world, without incurring significant financial costs for training. In addition, an important advantage of distance learning is the flexibility of learning. Students of distance courses can adapt the learning process to their needs and choose at the same time a convenient time for learning, which allows adults to study without interruption from work.

The main disadvantage of distance education, in our opinion, is the high labor costs of the teacher in preparing for classes. To organize the educational process online It is necessary to consider the presentation of the material, the ability to use the board, monitor the student’s completion of tasks in the notebook, or the use of third-party services for conducting classes. Most teachers use Skype to teach foreign languages. It is worth noting that the capabilities of Skype are limited only to the transmission of audio and video communications, and the use of chat to present new lexical and grammatical material. At the same time, there is no interactivity in the lessons; students’ perception of the educational material is more likely to lose than to gain.

There are currently several platforms for organizing the online learning process. One of the newest platforms created specifically for English teachers is progressme.ru. The platform was created for English language tutors who use a ready-made methodological program to conduct classes. The classes turn out to be interactive, since the teacher can not only use a special board for classes, but also use ready-made interactive tasks (videos, pictures, tasks with choices, etc.). Moreover, teachers will not need much time to prepare for such a lesson. However, this platform does not involve teaching two or more students at the same time. In addition, the creation of your own methodological developments on this platform is not provided. Another disadvantage of the platform is its cost. Most teachers are not willing to pay money for a limited service.

The issue of using distance learning technologies in a foreign language lesson still remains open. Despite the fact that the Internet platform as a didactic tool is in no way inferior to traditional didactic ones, and also allows for all traditional forms of training without loss of quality. However, most modern foreign language teachers still do not choose distance learning.

Based on the above, we can conclude that it is necessary to create a special platform that will meet all the needs and requirements of English teachers. First, it must be designed for group training. The second mandatory condition is the ability to create your own methodological developments, publish them on the platform and further use, and thirdly, it is necessary to create conditions for replenishing and updating the bank of tasks and selecting exercises from the methodological developments of other teachers. The main reason for creating such a platform is the fact that a foreign language teacher needs various services to conduct online classes, which are often not intuitive, and using them to prepare for a lesson will require time and special skills.

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